

Comparative Study of Strength Parameters on Concrete Made Using Expanded Polystyrene Beads, Lightweight Expanded Clay Aggregate and Waste Iron Chips

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KEYWORDS

Concrete, Expanded Polystyrene Beads, Lightweight Expanded Clay Aggregate, Waste Iron Chips, Admixture

ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for sustainable construction materials has led to extensive research in lightweight and eco-friendly concrete alternatives. This study investigates the comparative performance of concrete mixes incorporating Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) Beads, Lightweight Expanded Clay Aggregate (LECA), and Waste Iron Chips as partial replacements for conventional coarse aggregates. The primary objective is to evaluate and compare the strength characteristics—namely compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength—of these modified concrete mixes. Standard concrete mix designs were prepared, and varying proportions of EPS beads, LECA, and waste iron chips were introduced separately into different batches. All specimens were cast and cured under similar conditions, and strength tests were conducted at 7, 14, and 28 days. The results revealed significant variations in mechanical performance depending on the type of replacement material used. EPS and LECA contributed to reducing the overall density of concrete, making it suitable for lightweight applications, while waste iron chips enhanced certain strength parameters due to their high stiffness and interlocking properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is the most widely used construction material due to its high compressive strength, durability,

and versatility. However, the conventional production of concrete relies heavily on natural aggregates, leading to the depletion of natural resources and causing

significant environmental concerns. The increasing demand for sustainable and eco-friendly alternatives has led researchers to explore the feasibility of using lightweight and waste materials in concrete production. Lightweight concrete (LWC) is a specialized form of concrete characterized by a lower density compared to conventional concrete. This is achieved by incorporating lightweight aggregates or air voids within the concrete matrix. The primary motivation behind the development of LWC is to reduce the overall weight of structures without significantly compromising their strength and durability. LWC is widely used in applications where weight reduction is essential, such as in high-rise buildings, bridges, and precast structures. The reduction in self-weight not only minimizes structural loads but also enhances cost-effectiveness by reducing the need for extensive foundation systems. Various materials are used to produce LWC, including expanded polystyrene (EPS) beads, lightweight expanded clay aggregate (LECA), pumice, and perlite. These materials offer unique advantages such as improved thermal insulation, enhanced workability, and better acoustic properties. Additionally, LWC exhibits excellent resistance to seismic forces, making it a preferred choice in earthquake-prone regions. However, despite its benefits, challenges such as reduced compressive strength and higher water absorption rates must be addressed through optimized mix design and reinforcement techniques. This study investigates the feasibility of using EPS beads, LECA, and waste iron chips as alternative aggregates in lightweight concrete, assessing their impact on mechanical properties and structural performance. Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) beads, Lightweight Expanded Clay Aggregate (LECA), and Waste Iron Chips have emerged as potential substitutes for conventional coarse aggregate, offering a balance between strength and sustainability. EPS beads are lightweight and possess excellent thermal insulation properties, making them suitable for non-structural and lightweight applications. LECA, a lightweight aggregate, is known for its good strength-to-weight ratio and improved workability in concrete. On the other hand, Waste Iron Chips, a byproduct of the metalworking industry, can enhance the strength characteristics of concrete due to their metallic nature. By incorporating these materials in concrete, this study aims to analyze and compare their impact on the mechanical properties

of concrete, particularly in terms of compressive strength, flexural strength, and split tensile strength. Understanding these parameters will help determine the suitability of these materials in different construction applications, contributing to sustainable construction practices and reducing dependency on natural aggregates.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Effect of Expanded polystyrene (EPS) on Strength Parameters of Concrete as a Partial Replacement of Coarse Aggregates by Hitesh Patidar, Mayur Singi, Abhijeet Bhawsar (2019)- Patidar et al. (2019) conducted an extensive study on the effect of Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) as a partial replacement for coarse aggregates in concrete to address sustainability concerns and the increasing demand for construction materials. EPS, a lightweight and non-biodegradable material derived from packaging industries, presents an opportunity for sustainable concrete production. The research aimed to analyze the influence of varying percentages of EPS replacement (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%) in M30 and M40 grade concrete on key mechanical properties, including compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength. The study found that the incorporation of EPS significantly affects the density and mechanical properties of hardened concrete. As the percentage of EPS replacement increased, a reduction in compressive strength was observed, primarily due to the lower density and weaker bond between the polystyrene beads and cement matrix. However, the concrete mix demonstrated high workability even at low water-cement ratios, which can be beneficial for specific construction applications requiring lightweight concrete. The experimental results indicated that while EPS-modified concrete does not match the strength characteristics of conventional concrete, it offers advantages such as reduced self-weight and improved workability. This makes it suitable for non-load-bearing structures and insulation applications in the construction industry. The study emphasizes the potential of EPS in sustainable construction and highlights the necessity of optimizing mix proportions to achieve an ideal balance between strength and workability.

Physical and Mechanical Properties of a Bulk Lightweight Concrete with Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) Beads and Soft Marine Clay by Jianguo Wang, Bowen

Hu and Jia Hwei Soon (2019)- Wang et al. (2019) conducted a comprehensive study on the physical and mechanical properties of a bulk lightweight concrete incorporating Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) beads and soft marine clay. The research aimed to investigate the influence of EPS and cement content on mass density, stress-strain behavior, and compressive strength under varying confining pressures. The lightweight bulk filling material was fabricated using a combination of Singapore marine clay, ordinary Portland cement, and EPS beads, and was subjected to unconsolidated and undrained (UU) triaxial tests. Different mix ratios were examined, where the mass ratio of EPS beads to dry clay (E/S) was varied from 0% to 4%, and the cement-to-dry-clay ratio (C/S) was set at 10% and 15%. Additionally, the curing duration of the samples was considered, with tests conducted after three, seven, and 28 days. The study revealed that the mass density of the material was primarily influenced by the EPS content. An increase in EPS content from 0% to 4% resulted in a significant reduction in mass density—by 55.6% for the C/S ratio of 10% and by 54.9% for the C/S ratio of 15% after three curing days. Furthermore, shear failure was found to occur more easily in specimens with higher cement content and lower confining pressure. The research also established empirical relationships between compressive strength and mass density or failure strain using power functions. It was observed that increasing the cement content while reducing the EPS content led to an increase in both mass density and compressive strength. Additionally, the compressive strength demonstrated a logarithmic increase with curing time, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.83 to 0.97 across different confining pressures. These findings provide valuable empirical formulae for estimating the physical and mechanical behavior of lightweight concrete in various engineering applications, particularly in geotechnical and construction fields.

Light Weight Concrete by Using Eps Beads by Prof. Ashish S. Moon, Lokesh S. Selokar, Anuradha I. Patle (2020)- Moon et al. (2020) conducted a study on lightweight concrete using Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) beads to analyze its compressive strength and compare it with conventional concrete. The research aimed to evaluate the effect of incorporating EPS beads as a partial replacement of coarse aggregates in M25 grade concrete, following IS 10262:2009 guidelines. The study

also included the addition of 30% fly ash to enhance the properties of lightweight concrete. The experimental investigation involved preparing concrete cubes with varying EPS replacement levels—5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%—and testing their compressive strength after 7 and 28 days of curing. The results indicated that the compressive strength of the concrete decreased as the percentage of EPS beads increased. Among all tested samples, the mix with 5% EPS beads exhibited the highest compressive strength, with recorded values of 8 MPa and 11 MPa after 7 and 28 days of curing, respectively. This suggests that while EPS contributes to reducing the self-weight of concrete, excessive replacement negatively impacts strength due to the lightweight nature and low bonding capacity of EPS beads within the cement matrix. The study concluded that lightweight concrete with EPS beads can be an effective solution for non-structural applications, where reduced weight is a priority over high compressive strength. The findings also emphasize the need for an optimized mix proportion to balance weight reduction and mechanical performance in lightweight concrete applications.

The Effect of Expanded Glass and Crushed Expanded Polystyrene on the Performance Characteristics of Lightweight Concrete by Jurga Šeputytė-Jucikė, Sigita Vėjelis, Viktor Kizinievič (2023)- Šeputytė-Jucikė et al. (2023) investigated the performance characteristics of lightweight concrete (LWC) incorporating porous aggregates such as expanded glass (EG) from glass waste and crushed expanded polystyrene waste (CEPW) derived from packaging waste. The study aimed to evaluate the impact of these lightweight aggregates on the density, thermal conductivity, mechanical properties, water absorption, deformation behavior, and freeze-thaw resistance of LWC. The research focused on modifying the mix composition by varying the proportions of EG and CEPW while maintaining ordinary Portland cement (OPC) as the binder. The results demonstrated that incorporating CEPW led to a significant reduction in the thermal conductivity of LWC, decreasing from 0.0977 W/(mK) to 0.0720 W/(mK), making it more suitable for thermal insulation applications. Additionally, the presence of CEPW did not adversely affect the compressive and bending strengths, nor did it increase the water absorption of LWC. The freeze-thaw resistance of the LWC was

evaluated using two methods: one-side freezing and compressive strength reduction after 25, 100, and 200 freeze–thaw cycles. The findings showed that modifying the LWC structure with CEPW aggregates enhanced durability and reduced deformations, making it a promising material for sustainable and resilient construction.

Lightweight self-compacting concrete: A review by Suman Kumar Adhikary, Deepankar Kumar Ashish (2022)- Adhikary et al. (2022) reviewed the advancements in lightweight self-compacting concrete (LWSCC), highlighting its potential for structural and non-structural applications in civil engineering. The study focused on the effects of different types of lightweight aggregates (LWA) on the density, strength, and workability of LWSCC. The review found that larger cell sizes in lightweight aggregates tend to decrease density and mechanical strength. However, LWA contributes to internal curing, positively influencing cement hydration and improving long-term performance. Additionally, the study noted that incorporating nano-materials can enhance the strength properties of LWSCC, while the use of ultrafine particles reduces water absorption, leading to improved durability. It was demonstrated that LWSCC can be developed even with a density below 1000 kg/m³ while maintaining its self-compacting characteristics. Moreover, LWSCC exhibits excellent frost resistance, making it suitable for applications in extreme weather conditions. The review serves as a comprehensive resource for understanding the development and future prospects of LWSCC, promoting its broader acceptance in the construction industry.

Comparative Study on Light Weight Concrete by using Light Expanded Clay Aggregate and Pumice Stone by K. VarshaSri, G. Vishnu Vardhan, K. Swathi, D. Prasanna (2024)- VarshaSri et al. (2024) conducted a comparative study on lightweight concrete using light expanded clay aggregate (LECA) and pumice stone to improve compressive strength while reducing thickness and weight. The study aimed to analyze the properties of M20-grade lightweight concrete in both fresh and hardened states. The research involved the preparation of unique concrete mixes, with each mix containing three cubes and three cylinders to measure compressive and flexural strength. Additionally, the study investigated the effects of incorporating different mineral admixtures

into the concrete mixture. The experimental results demonstrated that strength and weight loss improved simultaneously across multiple trials. Among the materials tested, lightweight expanded clay aggregate (LECA) exhibited superior properties compared to pumice stone and conventional concrete, making it a more effective lightweight aggregate. The findings highlight the potential of LECA as a sustainable and efficient alternative in lightweight concrete applications.

Proportioning of Lightweight Concrete by the Inclusion of Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) by M. Gunavel, S. Aishwarya, K. Indhumathi, N. Jalapriya (2020)- This paper explores the characteristics of a novel lightweight concrete incorporating polystyrene, sand, cement, coarse aggregate, and water. The study introduces a simplified and cost-effective mixing method that eliminates the need for complex machinery systems, making it a promising approach for lightweight concrete applications. A key focus of this research is to determine the optimum dosage of Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) beads, which were incorporated into the concrete mix at varying proportions of 10%, 20%, and 30% by volume of fine aggregate. The mechanical properties, including compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength, were evaluated to assess the performance of the modified concrete. Based on the results obtained, it was observed that an optimal replacement of 10% EPS beads provides a balance between weight reduction and strength retention, making it a viable option for plain concrete structures where M25 grade concrete is typically used. The findings suggest that this lightweight concrete can be effectively utilized in construction applications requiring reduced density while maintaining adequate strength.

Physical and Mechanical Properties of Lightweight Expanded Clay Aggregate Concrete by Orkun Uysal, İlbüke Uslu, Can B. Aktaş (2024)- The porous nature of lightweight expanded clay aggregate (LECA) plays a crucial role in determining the physical and mechanical properties of concrete. This study presents a comprehensive experimental investigation involving 13 different mixtures and a total of 234 specimens, evaluating key parameters such as density, absorption capacity, porosity, compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, modulus of elasticity, and the impact of moisture state on LECA concrete. The results indicate that dry compressive strengths of the mixtures ranged

between 18 MPa and 38 MPa, with an average increase of 9% compared to moist compressive strength. Furthermore, the modulus of elasticity exhibited a significant reduction when the specimens were oven-dried, showing an average decrease of 26%. The study also critically examines existing modulus of elasticity prediction models, revealing that all models consistently overestimated the dry modulus of elasticity, which poses challenges for structural applications of LECA concrete. To address this issue, a novel predictive model for the modulus of elasticity was developed and validated using independent data from the literature, demonstrating its accuracy and potential for practical application.

A study on strength parameters of concrete with expanded fly ash clay aggregate by J. Bright Brabin Winsley, M. Muthukannan (2022)- For decades, significant advancements have been made in developing new processes to enhance the strength of concrete. In countries like India, materials such as fly ash and bottom ash have been widely used to reinforce construction work and serve as key components in Reinforced Cement Concrete (RCC). In recent years, civil engineers and industry professionals have increasingly turned to fly ash as a sustainable alternative for building construction. One of the notable developments in this field is the incorporation of Expanded Fly Ash Clay Aggregate (EFCA) alongside fly ash and bottom ash. This study investigates the use of EFCA in an M20 concrete mix, incorporating cement, fine aggregate, bottom ash, expanded fly ash clay aggregate, and coarse aggregate at respective proportions of 6%, 12%, 13%, 22%, and 25%. The research evaluates key strength parameters, including compressive strength and split tensile strength, with assessments conducted at curing intervals of 7 days, 28 days, and 56 days. Additionally, the flexural strength of the concrete mix was examined over these durations. The findings are analyzed based on the optimum dosage required for achieving the best balance between compressive strength and split tensile strength, providing valuable insights into the suitability of EFCA as a sustainable material for concrete applications.

Experimental Study on Light Weight Concrete by Using Light Expanded Clay Aggregate (LECA) by Arivalagan S, Dinesh Kumar K S A (2022)- This study investigates the structural behavior of lightweight concrete (LWAC)

incorporating light expanded clay aggregates (LECA) and normal-weight aggregates, focusing on the effect of partial and full replacement of coarse aggregate with LECA in an M25 concrete mix. The replacement levels considered in this research include 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, and 100%. The analysis was conducted in both the fresh and hardened states to evaluate the mechanical properties of the concrete, with a primary emphasis on performance parameters such as compressive strength and splitting tensile strength. The results indicate that the density of lightweight concrete varies between 1996 kg/m³ and 1597 kg/m³ as the LECA replacement increases from 40% to 100%. The study highlights that incorporating LECA significantly reduces the overall weight and cost of concrete by minimizing the dependency on conventional aggregates, making it a more economical and sustainable construction material.

Experimental study on strength and durability properties of iron scrap with fly ash-based concrete by R. Dharmara (2021)- Concrete is one of the most widely used materials in modern construction, primarily due to its versatility, durability, and cost-effectiveness. However, concerns about sustainability and resource efficiency have led researchers to explore alternative materials that enhance the mechanical properties of concrete while incorporating industrial waste products. Dharmaraj (2021) conducted an experimental study to analyze the impact of iron scrap and fly ash on the strength and durability properties of concrete. The research investigated the effects of varying percentages of iron scrap (ranging from 2.5% to 15% by volume) in an M20 concrete mix. The study demonstrated that incorporating iron scrap enhanced compressive and flexural strength, with an optimal aspect ratio of 100. Additionally, the inclusion of fly ash as a supplementary material further improved performance, contributing to increased sustainability in concrete production. The study further evaluated durability aspects such as Dorry's abrasion resistance, demonstrating the potential of iron scrap to enhance wear resistance in concrete applications. The findings suggest that utilizing industrial waste steel strips as reinforcement in concrete is both a cost-effective and structurally viable solution for various civil engineering applications. Several studies have explored the integration of alternative materials in concrete to improve mechanical properties and reduce environmental impact. Researchers have

previously investigated the influence of steel fibers and fly ash on concrete strength and durability, supporting the assertion that these materials can improve performance characteristics. The findings by Dharmaraj (2021) align with prior research indicating that industrial waste incorporation in concrete not only enhances strength but also promotes sustainability in construction practices.

Effect of Recycled Iron Powder as Fine Aggregate on the Mechanical, Durability, and High Temperature Behavior of Mortars by Md Jihad Miah, Md Kawzar Ali, Suwash Chandra Paul (2020)- Sustainable construction practices have increasingly focused on integrating industrial waste materials into cementitious composites to enhance mechanical performance and durability while reducing environmental impact. One such approach involves using recycled iron powder (RIP) as a replacement for natural sand (NS) in mortar, an area explored in recent research. Miah et al. (2020) investigated the effects of incorporating RIP as a fine aggregate in mortar, analyzing its mechanical strength, shrinkage behavior, durability, and residual compressive strength at elevated temperatures (20°C to 600°C). The study incorporated various replacement levels of NS with RIP (ranging from 0% to 50%) and found that an optimal replacement level of 30% resulted in significant improvements in mechanical properties. The 28-day compressive strength increased by 30%, tensile strength by 18%, and flexural strength by 47% compared to conventional mortar. Additionally, the inclusion of RIP led to reduced porosity (by 36%) and capillary water absorption (by 48%), indicating enhanced durability performance. The study also highlighted the thermal resistance of RIP-incorporated mortar, showing that strength degradation was more pronounced at temperatures above 250°C, especially for mixtures containing 50% RIP. Shrinkage behavior varied, with higher RIP content inducing both shrinkage and expansion effects. The research concludes that RIP, when used up to 30% replacement of NS, offers structural benefits while improving durability and sustainability in mortar applications.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

This study explores a novel approach to lightweight concrete, utilizing a simple and cost-effective mixing method that does not require complex machinery. The primary objective is to determine the optimum dosage of Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) beads in concrete. In this research, EPS beads were incorporated at 10%, 20%, and 30% replacement levels by volume of fine aggregate. The compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength of the concrete specimens were evaluated. Based on the results, it was observed that an optimal replacement of 10% EPS beads provides the best balance of strength and weight reduction. The study aims to examine the structural behavior of Lightweight Aggregate Concrete (LWAC) by incorporating Light Expanded Clay Aggregates (LECA) as a partial and full replacement for conventional coarse aggregates. The research focuses on investigating the effects of replacing coarse aggregate with LECA at varying percentages of 20%, 40%, and 60% in an M25 concrete mix. The study examines concrete mixes where M-Sand is replaced with steel chips at varying proportions (15%, 30%, and 60% by weight). The primary objective is to assess the impact of steel chip incorporation on key mechanical properties, including compressive strength, split-tensile strength, and flexural strength.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results- Concrete Made by Using Expanded Polystyrene Beads

Fig.4.1: Compressive Strength Test

Fig. 4.2: Split Tensile Strength

Fig. 4.3: Flexural Strength

4.2 Results- Concrete Made by Using Light Expanded Clay Aggregate (Leca)

Fig.4.4: Compressive strength for 28 Days

Fig.4.5: Split tensile strength for 28 Days

4.3 Results- Concrete Made By Using Waste Iron Chips

The waste steel chip concrete was produced by replacing fine aggregate with waste steel chips in varying proportions of 15%, 30%, and 60%.

Fig.4.6: Compressive Strength

Fig.4.7: Split Tensile Strength of Cylinders

Fig.4.8: Flexural Strength of Prisms

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the investigation of the effect of adding Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) as a partial replacement for fine aggregate in concrete, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The fineness of EPS and M-sand enhances the bonding between cement and aggregates, resulting in improved concrete quality.
2. Compressive strength increases with curing age; however, as the EPS content increases, the density and strength of the concrete decrease.
3. The split tensile strength decreases as the EPS replacement content increases.
4. Similarly, the flexural strength also decreases with higher EPS replacement.
5. Partial replacement of fine aggregate with EPS beads reduces the dead load, making it a lightweight concrete.
6. The optimal strength (compressive, split tensile, and flexural) was achieved at 10% EPS replacement. At 30% replacement, strength significantly reduces, but the concrete can still be used for single-floor buildings to improve cost efficiency and reduce dead load.

Based on the experimental results of this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The density of concrete decreases as the percentage replacement of normal aggregate with Light Expanded Clay Aggregate (LECA) increases.

2. The compressive strength and split tensile strength of concrete decrease with the increase in LECA content. Specifically, the compressive strength declines from 34.60 MPa to 21.77 MPa, while the split tensile strength reduces from 3.20 MPa to 1.50 MPa as the LECA content increases from 0% to 100%.
3. Concrete mixes incorporating 40% and 60% LECA replacement for coarse aggregates exhibit better performance compared to fully replaced LECA concrete and show improved results when compared to conventional concrete.

This study presents an experimental investigation to evaluate the properties of concrete specimens incorporating waste steel chips. The flexural strength, compressive strength, and split tensile strength of the modified concrete were analyzed.

1. Replacing M-Sand with waste steel chips at 15%, 30%, and 60% resulted in a reduction in concrete workability by 15%, 20%, and 24%, respectively.
2. The workability of the concrete was effectively improved by adding Glenium as a chemical admixture.
3. The strength of concrete increased progressively with higher percentages of waste steel chips replacing M-Sand.
4. Concrete incorporating waste steel chips demonstrated superior performance compared to conventional concrete.
5. The results confirm that the addition of waste steel chips enhances concrete strength without compromising its technical properties. Therefore, waste steel chips can be effectively utilized in the construction of residential buildings, footpaths, road dividers, parapet walls, and similar structures.

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Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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